

FAILURE OF CARBON FIBER-REINFORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES UNDER COMBINED LOADING

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ABSTRACT

Biaxial testing was performed on AS4/3501-6 graphite/epoxy composites to study their failure under combined loadings. Testing was performed in conjunction with a new miniature sandwich test specimen using combinations of axial tension and transverse compression, and axial compression and transverse compression. This specimen design allowed the generation of substantially higher transverse stresses in the composite than achievable with conventional test coupons. Axial load was applied in conventional test fixtures while the transverse load was applied independently through a hydraulically-driven loading device. The resulting data are compared with predictions from the Tsai-Wu failure theory and the maximum stress theory.

Keywords: Composite, biaxial testing, failure theory, sandwich specimen, compression strength.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most composite structures are made of multidirectional laminates and subjected to a variety of combined loadings. Each ply within a multidirectional laminate (or a unidirectional composite subjected to off-axis loads) experiences a combined state of stress even under uniaxial loading. Several failure theories have been proposed to predict the ultimate strength of composite laminates under combined loading. Considerable experimental work has been done testing materials under biaxial loadings to determine which of these failure theories can accurately predict the loads a structure can withstand. Some effort in this area has concentrated on the generation of a biaxial stress state from the uniaxial loading of off-axis specimens or multidirectional laminates. The transverse stresses generated in these tests, however, are a very small fraction of the axial stress. Most of the experimental work on combined loading has been limited to combinations of axial and transverse tension, or axial tension and in-plane shear, using cruciform-shaped test specimens [1] or composite tubes subjected to internal pressure [2]. These tests, in general, require expensive and complicated testing apparatus, while the specimens are also expensive to fabricate. Recently, a simplified, inexpensive testing device was designed to apply a combination of axial tension and transverse compression to a rectangular test coupon, and successfully employed in tests on aluminum [3]. Very little work has been reported in the technical literature on the combination of axial compression and transverse compression. The main reason for this is the difficulty in reliably determining the longitudinal compression strength of laminated composite plates due to the instability associated with the conventional test methods and specimens employed. Recently, we have developed a miniature sandwich test specimen to minimize or eliminate the instability problem. With this specimen we have obtained considerably higher compressive strengths for unidirectional carbon/epoxy, boron/epoxy and glass/epoxy composites than reported elsewhere in the literature [4].

The main objective of this investigation is to generate reliable failure data under combined loadings (mainly compression-compression and tension-compression) for the evaluation of existing

failure theories. To achieve this objective we conducted a series of experiments to generate failure data in the third and fourth quadrants of the failure surface in the longitudinal stress (σ_x) and transverse stress (σ_y) coordinates, and in the first and second quadrants of the failure surface in the transverse stress (σ_y) and in-plane shear stress (σ_s) coordinates. An attempt is made to fit the experimental data into a currently-available failure theory.

2. CALCULATION OF ULTIMATE STRENGTH

A number of failure criteria are available in the literature to predict the failure of laminated composites under a combination of applied loads. From among these failure criteria, the Tsai-Wu quadratic failure criterion [5] and the maximum stress criterion were selected. The former takes into account the interaction between the stress components and also offers the convenience of easy operation, while the latter does not consider any interaction between the stress components. For anisotropic materials, the Tsai-Wu failure criterion is given by

$$F_{ij}\sigma_i\sigma_j + F_i\sigma_i = 1 \quad (i, j = 1, 2, 6) \quad (1)$$

where F_{ij} and F_i are the strength parameters, and σ_i and σ_j are the stress components in the material axes. When the problem is limited to orthotropic materials under the plane stress state, Equation (1) assumes the following form:

$$F_{xx}\sigma_x^2 + F_{yy}\sigma_y^2 + 2F_{xy}\sigma_x\sigma_y + F_{ss}\sigma_s^2 + F_x\sigma_x + F_y\sigma_y + F_s\sigma_s = 1 \quad (2)$$

The strength parameters are determined from the material strengths and are given by

$$\begin{aligned} F_{xx} &= \frac{1}{XX'}, & F_x &= \frac{1}{X} - \frac{1}{X'} \\ F_{yy} &= \frac{1}{YY'}, & F_y &= \frac{1}{Y} - \frac{1}{Y'} \\ F_{ss} &= \frac{1}{SS'}, & F_s &= \frac{1}{S} - \frac{1}{S'} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where X and X' are the longitudinal tensile and compressive strengths, Y and Y' are the transverse tensile and compressive strengths, and S and S' are the positive and negative in-plane shear strengths, respectively. To ensure that the failure surface will intercept each stress axis, the magnitude of the F_{xy} term is constrained by the following inequality

$$F_{xx}F_{yy} - F_{xy}^2 \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

Because of the difficulty in experimentally determining F_{xy} , Tsai introduced a dimensionless parameter:

$$F_{xy}^* = \frac{F_{xy}}{\sqrt{F_{xx}F_{yy}}} \quad (5)$$

with bounds of -1 and 1.

The maximum stress criterion assumes that failure of the structural element subjected to a combined state of stress occurs when loading has reached such a value, that one of the principal stresses becomes equal to the uniaxial strength in tension, compression, or shear. If one of the following three principal stresses reaches the uniaxial strength, then failure occurs:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= X, \text{ if } \sigma_x > 0 \text{ or } |\sigma_x| = X', \text{ if } \sigma_x < 0 \\ \sigma_y &= Y, \text{ if } \sigma_y > 0 \text{ or } |\sigma_y| = Y', \text{ if } \sigma_y < 0 \\ \sigma_s &= S\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

For multidirectional laminates, the stress components in a ply within the laminate are calculated using laminated plate theory (taking the curing residual stresses into consideration) and are given by

$$\sigma_i = Q_{ij}A_{jk}^{-1}N_k + \sigma_i^R \quad (7)$$

where Q_{ij} and A_{ij} are the reduced ply stiffness and laminate stiffness, respectively, N_k are the applied laminate stress resultants, and σ_i^R are the ply residual stresses. The ply residual stresses within a laminate can be calculated by

$$\sigma_i^R = Q_{ij}(e_j^0 - e_j^T) \quad (8)$$

where e_j^0 and e_j^T are the laminate midplane thermal strains and the ply thermal strains, respectively, measured from the stress-free state.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material system used in this study was AS4/3501-6 (graphite/epoxy). Prepreg was obtained from the manufacturer in the form of unidirectional tape. The sandwich panels were composed of composite skins (or face sheets) two to eight plies thick, on either side of a neat resin core. These panels may be fabricated with prepreg skin and a gelled (or partially-cured) core simultaneously cured via the standard composite cure cycle, or in a two-step process, wherein neat epoxy resin is cast between prefabricated composite skins and cured at room temperature. Panels for this study were fabricated by both these techniques, details of which can be found elsewhere [4,6]. From microscopic examinations of panel cross sections both skin and core appeared free of voids. The fiber volume fraction of the composite skin, determined either by acid digestion or from photomicrographs at a number of locations in the panel, was found to be in the range of 60 to 65%.

All specimens were cut from these sandwich panels with care being taken to ensure alignment of the fibers with the specimen axis. Fiberglass/epoxy tabs were bonded to the specimen for gripping, and axial and transverse strain gages were mounted in the gage section. Figure 1 illustrates the

Figure 1. Geometry and Dimensions of a Miniature Sandwich Compression Specimen

geometry and dimensions of the sandwich specimen. Sandwich panels were made with the following laminate skins: $[0]_{4T}$, $[90]_{4T}$, $[0/90]_S$, and $[45/-45/90/0]_S$. In addition to sandwich specimens, $[45]_{20T}$ and $[60]_{20T}$ off-axis specimens were also sectioned from a $[0]_{20T}$ all-composite panel, and tested. Axial compressive and tensile loads were applied through an IITRI test fixture and a set of hydraulic grips, respectively. Transverse compressive loads were applied across the 12.7 mm gage

section with a hydraulically-driven loading device, using a pair of rubber-padded platens to generate a uniform compressive stress in the gage section of the specimen. The uniformity of this applied stress was examined using a rectangular aluminum specimen similar in dimensions to the test specimen. Three strain gages were mounted in the transverse direction, two on one face and one on the opposite face, to measure the strains arising from the transverse compression. Figure 2 shows a

Figure 2. Stress-Strain Relationships for an Aluminum Specimen used for Calibration of Load. (Symbols = experimental data from three strain gages; solid line = average value.)

plot of the strain versus applied compressive load for the three strain gages. The maximum difference in strain from these gages was found to be less than 12 percent. It was noted that the difference between the modulus determined from the average strain and the published value (73 GPa) for this aluminum (2024-T4) is less than 2 percent. Thus, it was not necessary to adjust the transverse load to compensate for friction loss between the rubber pad and specimen. The loading device is equipped with a strain gage-type load cell and is capable of generating up to 20 kN with a resolution of 7 N.

The specimen was first mounted in the axial test fixture, initially loaded in transverse compression to the prescribed level, and then stressed in the axial direction to failure while maintaining a constant transverse load. In some cases, the axial and transverse loads were alternately increased in small increments to the prescribed level, and the specimen was then stressed in either one direction to the failure, while maintaining a constant load in the other direction. Figure 3 shows a specimen mounted in the test fixture which in turn is mounted in the test machine. Both axial and

Figure 3. Photograph of the Experimental Test Set-up.

transverse loads and strains were monitored throughout the test. The applied stress in the composite skin was calculated from the rule of mixtures by the expression:

$$\sigma_s = \frac{1}{V_s}(\sigma_a - \epsilon_a E_c V_c) \quad (9)$$

where E , σ , ϵ , and V are the Young's modulus, stress, strain and volume fraction, respectively, and the subscripts s , a , and c represent the composite skin, entire specimen, and core, respectively. The modulus (secant) of the core in Equation 9 was adjusted to account for the nonlinear stress-strain behavior of the neat resin core, which is shown in Figure 4. The following material properties were experimentally determined and used in calculations.

Figure 4. Stress-strain behavior of neat epoxy resin.

$E_L = 140 \text{ GPa}$	$E_T = 10.0 \text{ GPa}$	$G_{LT} = 5.5 \text{ GPa}$
$\nu_{LT} = 0.3,$	$\alpha_T = 26 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$	$\alpha_L = -0.7 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C},$
$\Delta T = -153^\circ\text{C},$	$X = 1930 \text{ MPa}$	$X' = 1930 \text{ MPa},$
$Y = 52 \text{ MPa}$	$Y' = 207 \text{ MPa},$	$S = S' = 93 \text{ MPa}$

where E_L , E_T , and G_{LT} are the longitudinal, transverse, and shear moduli, respectively, ν_{LT} is the in-plane Poisson's ratio, α_L and α_T are the coefficients of thermal expansion in the longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively, and ΔT is the difference between the test (or room) temperature and the stress-free temperature.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 5 shows a typical failure of the $[45]_{20T}$ and $[60]_{20T}$ laminates. Failure occurs along the

Figure 5. Flat and edge views of typical failures of off-axis laminates under combined loading

fiber direction in all specimens, and appears to be initiated either in the gage section or under the tab. In both these laminates the transverse stress (tensile or compressive), shear stress, or combinations of these play significant roles in determining specimen failure under combined axial and transverse

loadings, with the stress component in the fiber direction exerting a very minimal influence. The stress component in the fiber direction at specimen failure was less than 10% of the average ultimate longitudinal strength. The transverse stress component and shear stress component in the material axes were calculated at the ultimate failure loads for comparison with the theoretical calculations from Equations 2 and 6, and the results are plotted in Figure 6. The failure envelope of Equation 2 was

Figure 6 . Comparison of experimental data with prediction in the $\sigma_y - \sigma_s$ space
A: Tsai-Wu failure criterion; **B:** Maximum stress criterion.

obtained by letting $\sigma_x = 0$ and using the material properties listed in previous section. Since the sign of the shear stress in this study is irrelevant to failure, and the failure envelope is symmetrical about the σ_y axis, all the negative shear stress data are converted to the positive shear stresses for the plot. From the plot the experimental data appears to agree reasonably well with the prediction from Eqn. 2.

The miniature sandwich test specimen stabilizes the composite against buckling (Figure 7), and also reduces stress concentrations at the ends of the gage section thereby promoting composite

Figure 7. Typical stress-strain curve for a sandwich specimen under uniaxial compression.
 Symbols: strains from back-to-back gages (no evidence of specimen buckling)

compressive failure in the gage section with consistent and significantly higher strengths. One difficulty in evaluating failure criteria is the generation of data away from the principal stress axes, because of limitations to the amount of transverse compressive load that can be applied to

conventional composite coupons. The smaller composite cross section of the sandwich specimen (by about a factor of six) translates to significantly higher transverse stresses for the same applied load. This feature has allowed the generation of failure data over a larger length of the predicted failure envelopes. Axial compression of unidirectional miniature sandwich specimens of this composite material typically produce composite failure in the gage section, at an angle of about 75° to the fiber direction [4]. Simultaneous transverse load application through the rubber-padded platens also produced the desired failure within the gage section, as shown in Figure 8. Sandwich specimens of the same dimensions were also tested under combined axial tension and transverse compression.

Figure 8. Typical failures of miniature sandwich specimens (with 2-ply unidirectional AS4/3501-6 skins) loaded in axial compression.

Strength data were gathered for [90]_{20T} composites and sandwich panels with [0]_{4T}, [90]_{4T}, [0/90]_S and [45/-45/90/0]_S composite skins, subjected to various static transverse compressive loads and failed under axial tensile or compressive loading. Transverse stresses in the composite skins were computed from the applied load and measured transverse strain. The stress components, σ_x and σ_y in the 0-degree ply of the [0/90]_S and [45/-45/0/90]_S composite skins are the values calculated by Equation 7 at specimen failure. It is noted that no shear stress exists in the 0-degree ply under axial and transverse loadings. The transverse stresses applied were selected to span as large a section of the failure envelope as possible. The resulting data are plotted in Figure 9. Also shown in this figure

Figure 9. Comparison of experimental data with prediction in the $\sigma_x - \sigma_y$ sp
 A: Tsai-Wu failure envelope with $F^*_{xy} = -0.25$, B: Tsai-Wu failure envelope with $F^*_{xy} = 0$, C: Maximum stress theory.

are the failure envelopes of the Tsai-Wu failure theory (with interaction parameters of 0 and -0.25) and the maximum stress theory. The limited data collected appears to fit the failure envelope of the

maximum stress theory reasonably well. However, these results do not include any in-plane shear data. Additional data are needed for this as well as other composite systems before any definite conclusions can be drawn.

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